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*Sven-Olof Yrjö Collin, Jenny Ahlberg***NEPOTISM IN FAMILY FIRMS – A TERMINOLOGY**

Nepotism is a central concept of family business since it constitutes the essence of a family business. In this paper, the first in a series of two, we present a terminology of nepotism in family firms making it possible to describe the extent and usage of nepotism in family business. Our view is that the family and the business are separate entities, but the family impregnates the corporation through supplying family members and here we define: nepotistic supply, generational nepotism, kin nepotism. Turning to the family corporation we define the concepts: nepotistic impregnation, nepotistic hierarchical diffusion, nepotistic functional diffusion. We claim that nepotism differs due to genetic distance, and due to gender, but it is also influenced by social conditions. We have speculatively argued that family members without genetic relatedness can be exposed to nepotistic treatment. We conclude that genetic nepotism can transform into social nepotism. We have presented clan and serial nepotism, and some allocative principles that reduce the full nepotism supply. Although nepotism could appear to be without any costs for the allocated individual, but allocative principles could be active, that reduce the negative sides of nepotism for the firm. We have suggested that there are links between nepotistic supply and nepotistic impregnation, influencing the environments acceptance of nepotistic actions. The analyses of the nepotism terminology proves that nepotism is not only the constitutive element of a family firm, but nepotism could also be a conscious strategy.

Key words: clan and serial nepotism, family firm, generational nepotism, kin nepotism, nepotism, nepotistic functional diffusion, nepotistic hierarchical diffusion, nepotistic impregnation.

Свен-Олоф Ирйо Коллин, Джени Ахлберг. Непотизм в семейных компаниях – терминология.

Непотизм – центральное понятие семейного бизнеса, поскольку является его сутью. В данной статье, первой в серии из двух статей, рассматривается основная терминология, касающаяся непотизма в семейных компаниях, для характеристики проявлений непотизма и того, как это отражается на семейном бизнесе. С нашей точки зрения семья и бизнес – это самостоятельные понятия, но, когда семья и ее члены становятся частью компании, мы говорим о семейственности в подборе кадров (nepotistic supply), преемственности поколений (generational nepotism), родовом непотизме (kin nepotism). При рассмотрении семейных предприятий, выделены такие термины как: концентрация непотизма (nepotistic

impregnation), иерархическая диффузия nepotизма (nepotistic hierarchical diffusion), административно-функциональный nepotизм (nepotistic functional diffusion). Утверждается, что на nepotизм влияют генетическая близость и половая принадлежность, так же, как и социальные условия. Выдвигается предположение, что nepotизм распространяться на членов семьи, которые не связаны кровными, а генетический nepotизм (преференции родственникам) может трансформироваться в социальный nepotизм. Выделены понятия клановый (clan nepotism) и семейный nepotизм (serial nepotism), а также принципы распределения позиций, связанные с заполнением вакансий в компании. Хотя распределение должностей среди родственников не требует вложения средств, для того чтобы избежать негативных последствий nepotизма для предприятия, нужно руководствоваться рассмотренными принципами. Предполагаемая связь между подбором кадров на основе nepotизма и концентрацией nepotизма влияет на то, как общество воспринимает протекционизм. Анализ терминологии nepotизма подтвердил, что nepotизм относится не только к деятельности семейных компаний, но и может также рассматриваться как целенаправленная и последовательная стратегия.

Ключевые слова: административно-функциональный nepotизм, иерархическая диффузия nepotизма, клановый и семейный nepotизм, концентрация nepotизма, nepotизм, преемственность поколений, родовой nepotизм, семейная компания.

Свен-Олоф Ирйо Коллин, Дженни Ахлберг. Nepotизм в сімейних компаніях – термінологія.

Nepotизм – центральне поняття сімейного бізнесу, оскільки це є його суттю. У даній статті, першій із серії з двох статей, розглянута основна термінологія, що стосується nepotизму в сімейних компаніях, для характеристики проявів nepotизму та того, як це впливає на сімейний бізнес. З нашого погляду сім'я та бізнес – це незалежні поняття, але, коли сім'я та її члени стають частиною компанії, ми кажемо про сімейність у підборі кадрів (nepotistic supply), наступність поколінь (generational nepotism), родовий nepotизм (kin nepotism). При розгляді сімейних підприємств, виділені такі терміни як: концентрація nepotизму (nepotistic impregnation), ієрархічна диффузія nepotизму (nepotistic hierarchical diffusion), адміністративно-функціональний nepotизм (nepotistic functional diffusion). Стверджується, що не nepotизм впливають генетична близькість та стать, як і соціальні умови. Припускається, що nepotизм поширюється і на членів сім'ї, які не пов'язані узами поколінь, генетичний nepotизм (преференції родичам) може трансформуватися у соціальний nepotизм. Виділені поняття клановий (clan nepotism) і сімейний nepotизм (serial nepotism), а також принципи

розподілення позицій, пов'язаний з заповненням вакансій в компанії. Попри те, що розподіл посад серед родичів не потребує вкладень, для уникнення негативних наслідків непотизму на підприємство, необхідно керуватися зазначеними принципами. Зв'язок між підбором кадрів на основі непотизму та концентрацією непотизму впливає на те, як суспільство сприймає протекціонізм. Аналіз термінології непотизму підтвердив, що непотизм стосується не тільки діяльності сімейних компаній, а й може розглядатися як цілеспрямована та послідовна стратегія.

Ключові слова: адміністративно-функціональний непотизм, ієрархічна дифузія непотизму, клановий і сімейний непотизм, концентрація непотизму, непотизм, наступність поколінь, родовий непотизм, сімейна компанія.

Introduction

In a family corporation, the ownership was transferred from the older family members to the middle generation. At the same time, a woman from the younger generation of the family was appointed vice CEO. In the newspapers, the transfer of the ownership was hailed as being an indication of continuity and a stable and responsible family firm strategy. At the same time, the promotion of the woman was stigmatized as an indication of nepotism.

These two events are both acts of nepotism, i.e., a tendency to treat individuals preferably due to family relationships, independently of contribution (Webb, Ketchen, & Ireland, 2010; Collin & Ahlberg, 2012), competence, productivity, or performance [26;]. Nepotism in the case of transfer of ownership was considered positive, but concerning promotion, it was considered negative. It is a paradox that nepotism, which defines a family firm, constituting its very essence and being one of the strongest driving forces of the family firm, to promote the family, can be so differently valued. And, more importantly, that the word describing both actions, nepotism, is considered to be a word with overly negative connotations (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012). Especially when it concerns gaining positions within the firm, there is a stigmatization of nepotism, as expressed by Mhatre, Riggio & Riggio, 2012, p.175: "...there is no such thing as 'good nepotism'".

Research, that is supposed to treat values with care (Myrdal, 1958), has treated it as either a negative force, for example, in an innovative twist of agency theory, claiming it to cause inefficiencies in terms of creating agency problems when hiring family members with lower competence than outsiders (Schulze, Lubatkin, Dino, & Buchholtz, 2001), or, on the other

side, inspired by resource and transaction costs theories, it has been claimed that nepotism increase certainty concerning the governance of the family firm (Webb et al, 2010).

Nepotism in science should, however, be treated without value claims, positive or negative. One method to reduce the value connotations of nepotism is to treat it as a concept that describes the family and the family firm, and especially the relationship between the family and the family firm. The aim of this paper is to describe nepotism through a created terminology of nepotism in family firms. Through the terminology we avoid the stigmatization of nepotism, and treat it only as a basic characteristic of the family firm. While terminological order is needed in a systematic treatment of a phenomenon, the application of the terminology shows its value. This endeavour is, however, reserved for a second paper (Collin & Ahlberg, forthcoming). Here we only present the terminology.

Terminology of nepotism in family business

Family business nepotism is the allocation of family members in the family business corporation. Nepotism in family business has two sides, the family that sends their family members, and the corporation that receives the family members. The border line between the family and the business is claimed to be vague and sometimes almost non-existent (Zattoni, Gnan, & Huse, 2015). Our view is that the family and the business are separate entities, but the family impregnates the corporation through supplying family members.

We will here give terms to some concepts aimed at describing the extent of nepotism, i.e., the allocation of family members in the corporation.

Figure 1 visualises the content of the concepts. The image describes the family and the corporation, both having vertical and horizontal dimensions.

Figure 1. **Terminology of family business nepotism**

Concerning family, the dimension of importance is the size of the family. This can be divided into two dimensions, where the vertical dimension is termed generation and consists of the number of generations existing, and the horizontal dimension of a family is termed kin and indicates the number of different blood lines.

In the case of the corporation, the dimension of importance is the size of the corporation in terms of positions that can be filled by family members. This can also be divided into two dimensions, where the horizontal dimension is termed nepotistic functional diffusion and the vertical is termed nepotistic hierarchical diffusion.

Beginning with the entity that supplies through nepotism, i.e., the family, we define:

Nepotistic supply: The number of family members supplied to the corporation. This involves all family members engaged in the corporation, from those family members being owners, to those that work during summertime in the factory of the corporation. It indicates to what extent the family is engaged in the corporation. While succession at the very top of the firm has been intensely studied, the overall supply of family members has received less attention (Muchinsky, 2012).

Generational nepotism: The number of generations of the family supplied to the corporation. This will indicate to what extent the family impregnates the corporation in terms of generations, i.e., if they have a strategy to specialize the generational involvement by sending only one or maybe two generations to the firm, or they involve all available generations. Generation appears as a frequent factor in family business research (e.g., Davis & Harveston, 1999; Lubatkin, Schulze, Ling & Dino, 2005).

Kin nepotism: The number of blood lines, i.e., kin relationships, that are engaged in the corporation. This indicates how many of the blood lines that the family exposes to the corporation, i.e., how the family impregnate the corporation with kin. This can appear in studies in some versions, such as Hamilton's r (Hamilton (1964a, b), i.e., the genetic distance between family members (Collin & Ahlberg, 2012) and as kin density (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012), which is a composite measurement containing Hamilton's r and what we later will term nepotistic impregnation.

These concepts of nepotistic supply aim to indicate to what extent the family is engaged in the corporation, on the dimensions that can be considered to be important, i.e., share of the family, generations and kin.

Turning to the receiving entity, the family corporation, we define the following concepts:

Nepotistic impregnation: The number of positions at the corporation that is occupied by family members. This indicates how the family dominates the corporation.

Nepotistic hierarchical diffusion: On which hierarchical levels family members appear. This is the vertical dimension of influence. Hierarchy is here defined as the ladder from share ownership, board membership, CEO, top management positions, divisional position, management position and worker position. It indicates to what extent the family distributes its members on governance, management, and labor positions.

Nepotistic functional diffusion: On which functional positions the family has representatives. This is the horizontal dimension of influence. It can be chair of the board, board member, deputy board member, or down in the organization with functional positions such as marketing or finance manager. It indicates to what extent the family has functional influence.

Terminologies could add value to conceptions if they manage to create distinctions that can add to our understanding of the phenomenon they

dissect. For example, our terminology could shed light on nepotistic strategies if one can find a firm with extensive kin nepotism and contrast it with a firm with reduced kin nepotism, for example, only using one of several available bloodlines of the family. Maybe reduced kin nepotism is a mean to keep conflicts low since rivalry between kin can be expected? Another example is the nepotistic hierarchical diffusion, where observation of a firm having very restricted diffusion, mainly to the governance level, ownership and the board, indicates a remote family engagement, which maybe even indicates a transformation of the firm from being a family firm.

We will, however, not focus on the usage of the terminology in this paper, but will continue our terminological ambition by discussing some aspects of nepotism, using the terminology but also expanding it.

Extension of terminology I: Genetic and social nepotism

Nepotism can be defined as a tendency to treat individuals preferably due to family relationships, independently of contribution (Webb, Ketchen, & Ireland, 2010; Collin & Ahlberg, 2012), competence, productivity or performance. This definition does not make any qualifications but treat all family members as equal and therefore subject to nepotistic treatment.

It has been found, however, that intensity in nepotism is gendered. Due to genetic uncertainty for males in their off-springs, nepotistic preferences differ due to gender. As expressed by Tanskanen & Danielsbacka (2012: 985): "...maternal grandparents and matrilinear kin in general are expected to increase child survival more than paternal grandparents and patrilineal kin..." Transforming to our subject it would claim that females would show more nepotistic actions than males.

Another variation of nepotism has been found in nepotistic intensity due to kin relationship, i.e., less nepotistic intensity when the genetic distance increase. This genetic influence on nepotistic intensity put also another distinction to the front, i.e., whether there is a social dimension of nepotism, or if it is confined to be purely genetic.

The intensity of nepotism could vary due to blood relationship, i.e., how genetically distant the family member is. A more qualified definition of nepotism would therefor include the Hamilton rule of inclusive selection. Hamilton (1964a, b, 1972) termed inclusive fitness those actions when an individual performs actions that promote the genes of the individual, but not necessarily the individual as such. When Titanic is sinking, inclusive selection is when the father or mother makes sure that the daughter and son

is in the lifeboat, and then they go to the restaurant in the sinking boat for the last drink. It is not the individual that is important, i.e., selfishness is not the leading principle, but the genes, i.e., the selfish gene, as a book title says, written by Richard Dawkins.

The idea of nepotistic inclusive selection, i.e., genetic nepotism, is that the engagement is relative to the genetic distance. The more distance, the less power of inclusive selection, simply because it does not promote the genes of the actor. For nepotism, this implies that nepotistic actions are stronger when it concerns kin that is genetically closer to the actor. When Titanic is sinking the mother or father first make sure that their children are in the lifeboat, then they look after their sister's and brother's children. Indeed, studies indicate that genetic distance and investments in children are correlated (Anderson, 2005; Coall, Hilbrand & Hertwig, 2014). Thus, we reserve the term, **genetic nepotism**, to actions where the nepotistic preference for family members is a function of the genetic distance.

However, there are situations when there is no genetic relationship, for example when individuals are married into the family and for adopted children. Adopted children have often no genetic similarity with the parents, thus the child should not receive any preferential action according to genetic nepotism. Indeed, studies have found less investment in adopted children (Case, Lin & McLanahan, 2000). But, while it is true that the adopted child has no genetic relatedness with the parents, it is still true that the child is socially the parent's child.

Imagine a family with individuals married into the family and with adopted children. Maybe, as indeed studies show, adopted children is not treated with the same preferences as the genetic individuals, they are still treated with higher preferences than compared to individuals in the extended family, such as kin. Thus, they experience a positive treatment, indicating a nepotistic action. If we find nepotistic acts in these cases, then we have found social nepotism, i.e., due to the social situation of the family, the individual, though not having genetic relationship, is treated with preference. If individuals can be treated with nepotism, without having genetic similarity, then genetic nepotism can be questioned.

But, what if social nepotism is the same as if there would be a genetic similarity? If adopted children will be treated the same way as genetic children, and that genetic cousins will be treated the same way as cousins that are adopted? Then we could claim that humans indeed have a nepotistic tendency, based on the genetic rule of Hamilton. This tendency

can, however, be fooled by identification, that humans identify a situation as asking for nepotism, and then create nepotistic actions. It is not a socially learned action, i.e., the act of nepotism is not influenced by values in society, that 'Thou shall treat relatives with care', but has its origin in the natural tendency of genetic nepotism. The nepotistic impulse is based on genetic distance, but it can be fooled and trigger nepotistic acts even if no genetic similarity is present.

This is to claim that nepotism, overall, is natural and not social. It is a strong force in human life. Indeed, it is so strong that it can overrule its basic origin, to support genetic survival. A mother or a father will put both the adopted son and the genetic daughter in the lifeboat before attending to others or themselves. It is nepotism as a natural instinct, overruling the genetic logic.

Two other factors can be presented, that influence variation in nepotistic action. They are the factors of interaction and vicinity (Sorenson, Goodpaster, Hedberg & Yu, 2009). Nepotism could be influenced by interaction and vicinity, in the manner, for example that two kin of the same blood, which could be expected to be treated similar due to genetic nepotism, will be differently treated due to one living as a neighbour, i.e., vicinity, and often attending family dinners, i.e., frequency of interaction, while the other lives remote and very seldom engage in family meetings. Vicinity makes it easier to evaluate the individual, thus influencing propensity to treat the person with preferences, and frequency of interactions does also give more information, but, maybe more important, show the individuals willingness to invest in the relationship.

Summarizing this section, we claim that nepotism differs due to genetic distance, i.e., genetic nepotism, and due to gender, but it is also influenced by social conditions, such as frequency of interaction and vicinity. We have speculatively argued that the genetic nepotism is so strong that it is fooled by itself, implying that family members without genetic relatedness can be exposed to nepotistic treatment. We conclude that genetic nepotism can transform into social nepotism.

Extension of terminology II: Regulation of nepotism through clan or serial nepotism

The nepotistic supply and the nepotistic impregnation meet at an interface, where the family meets the family firm. Since a family firm is a mean for supplying the family with resources, where one important resource is work and income opportunities, the firm has to offer positions

to the family members. This is the allocation of family members, but on what principles is the allocation performed?

If nepotism would be unlimited, one could expect that all willing family members (nepotistic supply) occupy positions in the family firm (nepotistic impregnation), i.e., nepotistic impregnation is but a function of nepotistic supply. Nepotism in this manner have created the criticism levelled against family firms, that they accept less competent individuals because they have one and only one characteristic, that of being member of the family (Schulze, Lubatkin, Dino & Buchholtz, 2001).

However, based on case experiences (Ahlberg, 2021) and with the recognition that family firms tend to survive in the competitive landscape of governance structures (Miller & Le Breton-Miller, 2006), there are reasons to expect a regulative mechanism that put a limit on the nepotistic supply, i.e., a principle of family member's allocation where the needs of the family are coordinated with the needs of the firm.

Considering the regulative principle, we distinguish between what we term clan nepotism and serial nepotism. **Clan nepotism**, inspired by the Ouchi (1979) concept of the clan, is when the family is characterised by individuals guided by a family solidarity, with a common system of family beliefs, and, in accordance with what Jaskiewicz et al (2013) term reciprocal nepotism, when there is substantial exchange of resources, be it labour, emotions and/or material. Jaskiewicz et al (2013) claim that this type of nepotism characterizes the family firm, which can exploit their nepotism in creating competitive advantage.

Serial nepotism is when the family is but a collection of individuals, organised as a serie (Sartre, 1960), lacking solidarity, but having a common interest organised through the family. It could be in accordance to the principle of primogeniture (Mhatre, Riggio & Riggio, 2012), as implemented in the fideicommissum, where the succession is predetermined, probably with lower performance as a consequence (Bloom & Reenen, 2007). Here we find what Jaskiewicz et al (2013) term entitlement nepotism, which is a condition of no exchange except for the pure genetic relation.

It is also possible to think that it is not the family firm that is a mean for the family, but the other way around, where the family is but a mean for the family firm. This is the occasion when the nepotistic impregnation is a function of the needs of the family firm, where the nepotistic supply feeds

the family firm with its needed resources of labour, applying an allocative principle that selects the family members for the firm.

The allocative principle of a family firm could be assumed to be governed by two objectives, one short term, to give support to the present family, with the risk of serial nepotism, and one long term, to secure the survival of the firm, based on clan nepotism. Both objectives are guided by nepotism in the sense that the family is at the centre of the objective.

Full nepotistic supply could be one allocative principle, where all interested individuals are given positions in the firm. This is when the firm is but a mean for the family.

Another allocative mechanism is the '*trial and error*' principle of family recruitment. Being a family member, you have the advantage of getting a position in the family firm. If you perform, you will stay, if you fail, you have to leave the firm. The family firm assumes the costs of trial and error. These costs are always present when recruiting any individuals, family or not family individuals, but since the selection is more based on merits and competence when it concerns non-family members, these costs can be assumed to be less than when recruiting family members. Additionally, a family member that does not perform creates two nepotistic costs, incompetence costs and moral dilution costs. Incompetence costs appear when the individual cannot perform the tasks of the position in acceptable manners. Moral dilution costs are the costs created through the reduced work ethics that can result when non-family employees experience that a family member receives advantages that is clearly not related to productivity, i.e., being unjustifiable (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012).

Another allocative mechanism is the '*dog treatment*', that a family member being employed will be put in a position of lower level than the competence would motivate, or in positions that are considered to be hard (Muchinsky, 2012). Two effects motivate the '*dog treatment*'. The family member has to earn the employment in the family firm through enduring the hardship. This will signal to the family that the employed family member can contribute to the survival of the family firm. It will also signal to the non-family employees that the family member is part of the team, the extended '*family*' of all employees, assuming the hardships of the firm.

One allocative mechanism on the side of nepotistic impregnation is *flexibility*. While ordinary employees have to follow contracts and regulations, family members can be used more flexible. Family members

are supposed to give to the firm when the firm has its needs, in accordance with their clan nepotism (Jaskiewicz et al, 2013) and in accordance to Kragh's (2012) claim, that a family member has to show solidarity, lacking short-term utilitarian objectives. Flexibility implies that the family member has to perform the work that needs to be done, independent on formal contract, and that the family members salary could vary due to the firm's capacity to carry the salary. The flexibility is just an aspect of the fuzzy border between the family and the firm that is so characteristic of family firms, including family members experiencing an insignificant border between their family lives and their lives as employees of the firm (Muchinsky, 2012)

Summarizing, we have presented clan and serial nepotism, and some allocative principles that reduce the full nepotism supply, where the firm is but a mean for the family, into a situation where the needs of the firm is also considered. They were the principle of '*trial and error*', '*dog treatment*' and of '*flexibility*'. The conclusion is that at quick glance, nepotism could appear to be without any costs for the allocated individual, but allocative principles could be active, that reduce the negative sides of nepotism for the firm.

Extension of terminology III: Acceptance of nepotism through balancing nepotism supply and nepotism impregnation

Family firms exist in the whole size range, from the smallest local firms, to the largest, international listed corporations. The occurrence of nepotistic impregnation could, however, differ due to size. In a study of CEO careers Salvato, Minichilli & Piccarreta (2012) found that most firms in their sample were managed by non-family CEOs, which they partly explained by the institutional pressure the firms are experiencing.

Could it be the case that there are norms of nepotistic impregnation that differ between large, listed publicly observed corporations and smaller corporations, that only exists in a local context and in their business relationships?

It has been found that family firms use their character of family firm as a marketing tool, both towards customers and towards factor suppliers, such as credit and labour suppliers. In these cases, there appears not to be an institutional pressure against nepotistic impregnation in family firms. On the contrary, they appear to exploit the impression of family firms as being more long term and more stable by using nepotism as a marketing tool. Nepotism could thus be seen as a reputation investment.

What happens when a firm grows to the size of the large and listed corporation is that they tend to be more exposed to mass media and political interest on a national level. It could speculatively be suggested that there exists a norm system on this level that deems nepotism, especially positional nepotism, negative. This norm against positional nepotism will reduce the nepotistic impregnation of the firm. Thus, the firm has to find a balance between nepotistic impregnation creating the positive reputational effect and the negative effect created by positional nepotism.

It could also be that the nepotism in ownership of the firm becomes so much diluted that the reputational effect of family character that discipline family actors becomes too weak. This will transform the family firm into an object of exploitation by distant family members. There will be a conversion from clan nepotism, which is a supportive nepotism, to serial nepotism, which contains relationships of an exploitive character (Jaskiewicz, Uhlenbruck, Balkin & Reay, 2013). Thus, there are some points in the development of the family firm when the bad sides of family firms can become dominant.

It can be hypothesised that this point is reached when considering the dilution of ownership in relation to the nepotistic impregnation. As long as the kin is equally engaged in the ownership and the operations of the firm, maybe especially on higher hierarchical positions, there is a positive reputational effect. But the reputational effect will be reduced when there is no relation between the ownership and the operational positions. Then both the owners and the operationally active family members will increase in opportunism, mainly in disinterest in long term engagement.

If this is correct it is not institutional differences or size per se that is active, but the relationship between nepotistic supply, especially kin nepotism, and nepotistic impregnation, maybe especially nepotistic hierarchical diffusion. A proposition could be suggested that the environment's acceptance of nepotism is driven by the relatedness between kin nepotism and hierarchical nepotism. The more the family shows engagement in both ownership and positions, the more their nepotism will be accepted and even constitute a marketing tool, to gain the brand of family firm. Thus, acceptance of nepotism is independent of size and institutional milieu, but dependent on the family's capacity to link kin nepotism with positional nepotism.

Summarizing, we have here, speculatively, argued that there are links between nepotistic supply and nepotistic impregnation, influencing the

environments acceptance of nepotistic actions. It indicates that the family and the family firm can use nepotism as part of a firm strategy.

Conclusion

We have suggested that nepotism is the essence of family firms and presented a terminology making it possible to analyse nepotism through nepotistic supply and impregnation. We have presented some propositions when further analysing the nepotism terminology, that together create the conclusion that nepotism is not only the constitutive element of a family firm, but nepotism could also be a conscious strategy.

However, the value of a terminology lies not only in its ability to create order in and between concepts, but the value consists first and foremost in its ability to create an understanding of empirical cases by being an analytical instrument. Thus, we need empirical studies using the terminology. Only then can we evaluate the value of the proposed terminology.

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